

The panchromatic view of galaxy build-up in the first 2 Gyr of cosmic history

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Over the past decades, several important steps have been taken to understand the formation and evolution of first generations of galaxies. Thanks to deep multi-wavelength observations by Hubble Space Telescope (HST), studies of early galaxies have now been pushed well into the Epoch of Reionization, i.e. up to $z \sim 10 - 11$ only 500 Myr after the Big Bang [1, 2, 3]. However, our current knowledge beyond $z \sim 2 - 3$ is significantly biased to the rest-frame ultraviolet observations as it's only accessible by deep optical/near-infrared observations, and dust-obscured properties of high-redshift galaxies have remained mostly unknown. This situation was revolutionized by extremely sensitive and high-resolution far-infrared (FIR) interferometers such as ALMA and NOEMA. First ALMA observations showed us surprises by finding fainter FIR emission than expected from low-redshift galaxy observations, suggesting an evolution of dust-obscured galaxy properties at high-redshift [4, 5]. To understand this potential evolution with statistical samples and with a wide range of galaxy parameters, large ALMA observations were required. In the Hypatia colloquium, I discussed the evolution of dust-obscured star-formation of galaxies at $z \sim 3$ to $z \sim 6$ revealed by ALMA, including a recent ALMA large program: ALPINE. Furthermore, I also discussed newly found heavily dust-obscured galaxies in the epoch of reionization (EoR) from the on-going ALMA large program: REBELS. The newly found dusty galaxies are serendipitously found as companions of UV bright main-sequence galaxies at $z \sim 7$. Given the limited survey volume, they suggest an additional 10 – 25 % contribution to the cosmic star-formation rate density. These studies of dust attenuation properties and dust-obscured star-formation are crucial to interpret existing and upcoming observations, including upcoming very high-redshift galaxy observations by James Webb Space Telescope.

Dust Attenuation Properties of Star-Forming Galaxies at $z > 4$

To understand galaxy formation and evolution, star-formation rates (SFRs) of galaxies are one of the most fundamental parameters. For high-redshift galaxies, measuring SFRs of galaxies are largely based on the galaxy's rest frame ultraviolet (UV) emission which is generated by short-lived massive stars (i.e., O- or B-stars). As the UV emission is easily attenuated by interstellar dust, the dust attenuation correction is crucial to provide accurate total SFRs of galaxies.

To correct dust attenuation, there are mainly two methods: (1) direct observations of dust by infrared wavelengths, and (2) estimating dust attenuated UV emission by empirically calibrated relation. Because of

its accessibility, one of the empirically calibrated relations is frequently used for high-redshift galaxies, which is known as the IRX- β relation [7]. The IRX- β relation is a powerful tool as one can perform dust attenuation correction only by a few photometry in the rest-frame UV emission. However, the relation is only calibrated using high-redshift analogue galaxies in the local Universe, and it is still unknown if the locally calibrated relation is really applicable to high-redshift galaxies.

Figure 1: IRX- β relation obtained in the ALPINE survey [6]. The newly obtained relation suggests an evolution of dust attenuation properties of star-forming galaxies at $z > 4$, suggesting SMC-like dust attenuation properties and bluer intrinsic UV spectral slope.

The recent ALMA large program: ALPINE is an ideal opportunity to study dust attenuation properties of high-redshift galaxies. In the ALPINE survey, we targeted 118 main-sequence star-forming galaxies at $z = 4.5 - 6$, and observed [CII] $158 \mu\text{m}$ emission line and dust continuum. As a result, we obtained 23 individual dust continuum detections. Using the dust continuum observations, we created IRX- β of the target galaxies, which provided us the dust attenuation relation directly using high-redshift galaxies.

The resulting IRX- β relation (Figure 1) shows that locally calibrated relation is not applicable to $z > 4$ galaxies, and prefers bluer intrinsic UV slope (β) and flatter slope of the IRX- β relation. This suggests that dust attenuation properties of high-redshift galaxies are represented by a steep attenuation curve in UV emission, similar to or even steeper than dust extinction curve observed in the SMC.

At the same time, the observed low IR luminosity suggests the low obscured fraction of star-formation activities ($f_{\text{obs}} = \text{SFR}_{\text{IR}}/\text{SFR}_{\text{tot}}$). For massive galaxies with $\log M_*/M_\odot > 10$, the observed f_{obs} at $z \sim 5.5$ is around 50%, while the f_{obs} at $z < 3$ is $\sim 90\%$ [8]. This suggests rapid build-up of dust-obscured star-formation activity between $z \sim 5.5$ to $z \sim 3$ Universe. Further ALMA surveys to observe high-redshift galaxies are required to confirm and extend the newly found evolution from the ALPINE survey.

Dust-obscured Star-Formation Activities in the Epoch of Reionization

In the EoR, heavily dust-obscured galaxies are known to be limited to the extreme starburst galaxies [9] and companions of rare quasars [10]. These studies conclude that the contribution of dust-obscured galaxies to the cosmic star formation rate density at $z > 6$ is sub-dominant. Recent ALMA and Spitzer observations have identified a more abundant, less extreme population of obscured "optically-dark" galaxies at $z = 3 - 6$ [11]. However, this population has not been confirmed in the EoR so far.

In the latest ALMA large program, REBELS, we observed 40 main-sequence star-forming galaxies at $z = 6.5 - 9$ to scan [CII] $158 \mu\text{m}$ or [OIII] $88 \mu\text{m}$ emission lines. From two of the REBELS targets, REBELS-29 and REBELS-12, we identified serendipitous emission lines and dust continuum as companions of $z \sim 7$ galaxies (Figure 2). Although estimated SFRs and stellar masses are consistent with the main-sequence of $z \sim 7$ galaxies, these serendipitously found galaxies are completely absent from rest-frame UV images. This suggests that the newly found galaxies are heavily dust-obscured, but otherwise "normal" galaxies in the EoR. The finding of less extreme dusty star-forming galaxies in the clustered environments shows that we are still missing a significant amount of star-formation activities in the EoR. Although uncertain, after correcting clustering, current estimates suggest an additional 10 – 25% contribution to the cosmic star-formation rate density.

The complete census of star-formation activities is clearly a prerequisite to understand the cosmic reionization. Further deep and wide field surveys by ALMA and JWST are essential to confirm number density of the heavily dust-obscured galaxy population, and to study how galaxies formed and evolved in the EoR.

Conclusion

Compared to the rest-frame UV observations, the infrared observation of high-redshift galaxies is still highly incomplete despite 10 years of ALMA operations with

large amounts of scientific discoveries. However, we started to find several important properties of high-redshift galaxies, and our ALMA observations are becoming more and more efficient given the past experience and findings. In the next 10 years, we will be able to see more rapid progress of our understanding of high-redshift galaxies with strong synergy of ALMA and JWST.

Figure 2: Two heavily dust-obscured, but otherwise "normal" galaxies are identified as companions of main-sequence galaxies at $z \sim 7$ [12]. The detections from tiny survey volume suggest the wide-spread existence of such dusty galaxies in the epoch of reionization.

At the same time, several on-going projects to build extremely sensitive and large single dish millimeter/submillimeter telescopes (such as Large Submillimeter Telescope; LST[¶]) will provide complementary observation with their large field of view in the future. The JWST and future telescope plans will make our high-redshift galaxy view more complete, and our current study will pave the way to our future understanding of galaxy formation and evolution throughout cosmic history.

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